

*Cristina Țurac-Drahta
Faculty of Letters and Communication Sciences,
Ștefan cel Mare University of Suceava,
13 Universității Street, 720229
Suceava, Romania
e-mail: cdrahta@yahoo.fr

ANDREI MAKINE'S *ENTRE-DEUX-MONDES*:
DUALITY AND (MIS)ADJUSTMENT

Abstract

After fleeing from the Soviet Union to live and write in France, Andrei Makine denounces in his first nine novels the atrocities perpetrated by the Bolshevik regime and accomplishes what he considers to be a writer's role: provoking readers to think about events that took place in recent history. He places his characters in a complex cultural background and endows them with a double perspective on life. The *entre-deux-mondes* pattern he creates applies to issues such as identity, civilization, language and general outlook on things.

Keywords: *entre-deux-mondes*, the Soviet Union, anti-communism in literature

Introduction

Having left his fatherland, Russia, for France, around 1987, Andrei Makine turns it into a major topic in his first novels, paying a sort of tribute in describing recent wounds of the Russian soul. More specifically, he dedicates his first nine novels to the Soviet Russia and to denouncing the avatars of this totalitarian regime. He delivers his message through a bunch of heroes, his narrators, who sometimes remain nameless.

Vacillating between two worlds, his native Russia and France, his country of adoption, he imbues his fiction with this duality, with this *entre-deux-mondes* [between two worlds], as he calls it in two of his novels.

In this paper, we underline the way this fluctuation can be seen in the hesitation between two complementary dominant features, more precisely we break down this *entre-deux-mondes* pattern into: *two identities, two civilizations, two languages and two outlooks*.

This oscillation is obvious especially in the first nine novels written between 1990 and 2004 and published in Paris and we believe that the classification we propose in this short literary investigation contributes to a better understanding of the splitting between two worlds. Furthermore, his narrators and his characters subtly unveil certain episodes of their author's existence thus creating a quasi-biography of Andrei Makine (this author born in 1957 in Krasnoyarsk, Siberia, who is so reluctant to give details about his own personal life).

As follows we will cast a glance at the episodes where these features fit and hope to incite the readers' curiosity about this fascinating author (a member of the French Academy since 2016), and about his novels which have all been translated into English by Geoffrey Strachan.

*Cristina Țurac-Drahta is a Lecturer, PhD, author of a thesis on Russian-born French novelist Andrei Makine. She is a member of the French Department of the *Ștefan cel Mare* University of Suceava where she teaches French 17th century literature and gives lectures on Translation Studies. She is also interested in religious translation.

Two Identities

Keeping in mind that the action of all novels is set in the Soviet Union, the two identities in question here are the Russian one – native – and the French one – largely considered superior. The Russian identity, often perceived as imperfect, needs a French transplant that becomes unbearable as it ends up emphasizing precisely the main identity. With Makine, the question of the self is best represented in Aliocha's confrontation with his Russian alter-ego (*Le testament français / Dreams of My Russian Summers*). The young Siberian boy, Aliocha, equipped with this French identity transmitted by his grandmother, Charlotte Lemonnier, sees himself armed with this “greffe française” (Makine, 1995: 184) [French transplant] and becomes a “Frantzouz” (Makine, 1995: 221). Oscillating between this double identity affiliation, being alternatively proud and disdainful, the main character of the novel ends up feeling this strange burden and considering he has become “un étrange mutant” (Makine, 1995: 223).

But my greatest initiation that summer was to understand how one could be French. The countless facets of this elusive identity had formed themselves into a living whole. It was a very well ordered mode of existence, despite its eccentric aspects. France was for me no longer a simple collection of curios but a tangible and solid entity of which a small part had one day been implanted inside me. (Makine, 2011: 85)

Russia, like a bear after a long winter, was awakening with me. A pitiless, beautiful, absurd, unique Russia. A Russia pitted against the rest of the world by its somber destiny. Yes, if I had occasion to weep at the death of my parents, it was because I felt Russian. And the French graft in my heart began, at times, to give me great pain. (Makine, 2011: 142)

A young pianist in *La musique d'une vie / Music of a Life*, Alexeï Berg, is forced to give up his identity and his ambitious projects and chooses to take the place of the soldier Sergueï Maltsev, a dead soldier on a battlefield in Ukraine during the second World War.

One day he saw a man asleep, drunk, at the foot of this fence, lying there as if felled by a rifle shot. The panels of his jacket were spread out in the dust of the road; his snores reached all the way to the barn. This slumped body expressed such a blithe indifference to what anyone might think of him, such a lack of constraint in this temporary death, such a physical oblivion, that Alexeï became aware of a violent jealousy. Or rather, of a temptation: to lay hands on this snoring corpse, search him, rob him of his papers, disguise himself in his clothes, return to life under this stolen name... The splinters in the wooden plank pricked his cheek. Alexeï stared at the drunkard as if this were a miraculous vision. The man was nothing like him, at least twice as old as he was, red-haired, with a flat nose. But this notion of stealing an identity, unlikely as it seemed for the moment, took root in his memory. (Makine, 2004: 51-52)

The fear of oppression is more powerful than the desire to survive, so the young pianist's main preoccupation is not with staying alive during the war, but with suppressing any uncontrolled reaction that could betray him:

Alexeï stopped beside the piano, let a hand come down on the keyboard, listened, closed the lid again. His joy of not feeling within himself the presence of a young man in love with music was very reassuring. He looked at his hand, the fingers covered in scars and scratches, the palm with its yellowish calluses. Another man's hand. In a book, he thought, a man in his situation would have rushed to the piano and played it, forgetting everything, weeping perhaps. He smiled. Such a thought, such a bookish notion, was probably the only link that still bound him to his past. (Makine, 2004: 64)

Individuality acquires political connotations in the case of the military physician in *Requiem pour l'Est*, whose parents had been executed as “traitors” and who decides to become a Soviet spy in order to acquire a spotless identity. Brought up in little fortune, studying foreign languages in Moscow, Olia, the

daughter of a Soviet Union hero, ends up being a prostitute at the mercy of the Soviet regime. In the novel *Confession d'un porte-drapeau déchu*, having crossed the ocean, Kim and Arkadi discuss the controversial assimilation of a Russian by the American people.

Identity as it comes into being is presented in *La Terre et le ciel de Jacques Dorme*, the narrator of which is in search of accomplishment in a library. While travelling by train to the Far East, the three teenagers in *Au Temps du fleuve Amour*, Dimitri, Outkine and Samouraï, become transfigured as a result of meeting the Occident, and they develop into the Lover, the Poet and the Warrior. Véra, from *La Femme qui attendait*, wishes she could make up for the lost time and throws herself into a love affair with a young intellectual from Leningrad. Olga Arbélina is the victim of an “unspeakable intimacy” as, being a librarian near Paris, a devoted mother to her son suffering from haemophilia, she accepts this affair but is constantly reprimanded by an inner voice.

The identity paradigm plays a fundamental role in Makine’s novels as, torn between a social identity and a cultural one, his characters distinguish themselves by this dominant feature that seems to unite them all in one single voice.

Daniel Sibony (2003, n.p.) testifies to this reality: “In these times of great subjective and collective identity discomforts, where borders vacillate, where identity is a problem – sometimes it capsizes and sometimes it tenses up – we were surprised to discover that the concept of difference is also insufficient to account for all this effervescence: it is too simple, too rigid.”

Two Civilizations

The pattern of the two civilizations, of cultural distinction, illustrates the perfect oscillation between the two universes, namely the Russian one and the Western (prevalently French) one. The Western world, this promised land, represents an inescapable enchantment for Makine’s characters.

The object of conflict between the two civilizations is best represented by the narrator of *La Terre et le ciel de Jacques Dorme*, caught between the daily Soviet reality and the fictional image he has of France – this “extraterrestrial” civilization. Also, the three teenagers in *Au Temps du fleuve Amour* display an extreme admiration for the Occident, personified by the actor Jean-Paul Belmondo, that they had seen at the cinema. For the young man playing a *Requiem pour l’Est*, the Occident is a heart-rending reality as, on the one hand, he is saved by a French friend, but on the other, his dreams of love are crushed in Florida.

Coming from a “monstrous land” – the Soviet Union, Aliocha from *Le testament français* simultaneously rejects and accepts his destiny of grandson of a French woman displaced in Russia and of offspring of a shattering Soviet Union. Living in a civilization full of constraints and admiring the other – free and disinhibited, the young man accepts this civilizational transfer. Later on, when France rejects a “moujik” who writes perfectly in French, the writer has no hesitation in presenting this country as a priceless cultural founder. France is therefore a “fictional land”, a means of evasion from another realm. France is the land of all opportunities which hosts Aliocha’s literary success in the end.

For the first time in my life I was looking at my country from the outside, from a distance, as if I were no longer a part of it. Transported to a great European capital, I looked back to contemplate the immensity of the cornfields and the snow-covered plains by moonlight. I was seeing Russia in French! I was somewhere else. Outside my Russian life. To be thus torn asunder was so painful and at the same time so thrilling that I had to close my eyes. I was afraid of not being able to return to myself, of being stranded in that Parisian evening. Screwing up my eyes, I inhaled deeply. The warm wind of the nocturnal steppe suffused my being once more. (Makine, 2011: 33)

The young boy lives nevertheless in a very immediate Russia that spreads its heavy dark wings over every breathing creature. When he is queuing in a store in order to purchase the rationed goods he is allowed to, the crown cruelly wants to eliminate him and his sister, so he succeeds in detaching himself from this universe and embracing the other world he belongs to:

I had joined an interminable queue that wound round outside the premises of a food shop, crossed the threshold, and then extended inside it. It was all, no doubt, for some foodstuff rare in winter – oranges or perhaps simply apples, I no longer recall. I had already passed the most important psychological milestone of this wait, entering the door of the shop, outside of which dozens of people were still squelching about in muddy snow. It was at that moment that my sister came to join me: as two people, we were entitled to a double quantity of the rationed goods.

We did not understand what suddenly provoked the anger of the crowd. The people standing behind us must have thought that my sister was trying to worm her way in without queuing – an unforgivable crime! Angry shouts erupted: the long snake contracted, threatening faces surrounded us. We both tried to explain we were brother and sister. But the crowd never admits a mistake. (Makine, 2011: 39)

Aggrieved and chased away by a revolutionary Russia, Olga Arbélina is welcomed by a glamorous France that encourages her to integrate herself. Ironically, she runs away from an abusive country in order to find shelter in another country, where she tacitly suffers her sick son's unspeakable abuse. The lures of civilization are the very cradle of folly, as this is Olga's crime after all.

In *Confession d'un porte-drapeau déchu*, the people in the small town of Sestrovsk see in New York the land of welfare. For Olia, the prostitute-translator, the Occident is compromising, as she is discovered by the KGB in the arms of a Frenchman whom she had seen as a redeemer. Life brings Arkadi, the kid from the community of Sestrovsk, to the United States, where he is accepted and succeeds in integrating himself. However, his friend, Kim, the narrator of *Confession d'un porte-drapeau déchu*, based in Paris, considers that this discrepancy between the two civilizations is overwhelmingly crushing and mistrusts Arkadi, assuming he fakes assimilation, as the Russian past comes to light and demands recognition within the American wellbeing.

Two Languages

Makine's universe is projected onto a dual linguistic context where the French language is paramount. As the Soviet Union imposes Russian as the only unifying official language, the French language is often a vehicle of evasion and of survival in the totalitarian nightmare.

The Siberian Aliocha is tormented by the vacillation between two languages, as he adopts French in the *Testament français* as his “grand-mother's language” and “domestic slang”, in order to achieve his literary consecration.

The narrator of *Requiem pour l'Est* is saved from the Stalinian terror during his childhood thanks to a lullaby sung in French, a language which he will later use in his profession. Another orphan, in *La Terre et le ciel de Jacques Dorme*, succeeds in recuperating the maternal love he lacked as a child by reading in French the volumes he finds in a library. For the three teenagers in love with the Occident and with Belmondo, French is a primordial language, a language around which all the other languages gravitate.

Two Outlooks

Carrying around all these dualities, Makine's protagonists are also torn between the two outlooks testifying to the substantial fluctuation we deal with in the present paper. For Charlotte Lemonnier's grandson, czar Nicholas the Second's figure is subject to troubling controversies as in class at school this personality is presented as a “bloody tyrant” responsible for abominable crimes (according to the History teacher preoccupied with underlining the glory of the Bolshevik revolution), whereas his grandmother depicts a Parisian ball where the same czar Nicholas had been a guest of honour. Later on, when Charlotte opens up about her native town, Neuilly-sur-Seine, Aliocha imagines it as a typical Siberian village, creating a splendid naïve image with elements from rural common life: izbas, a yoke, a herd of animals etc.

Neuilly-sur-Seine was composed of a dozen log cabins. Real izbas, with roofs covered in slender laths, silvered by the rigors of winter, with windows set in prettily carved wooden frames and hedges with washing hung to dry on them. Young women carried full pails on yokes that spilled a few drops on the dust of the main street. Men loaded heavy sacks of corn onto a wagon. A slow herd streamed idly toward the cowshed. We heard the heavy sound of their bells and the hoarse crowing of a cock. The agreeable smell of a wood fire – the smell of supper almost ready – hung in the air.

For our grandmother had indeed said to us one day, when speaking of her birthplace, “Oh ! At that time, Neuilly was just a village... “

She had said it in French, but we only knew Russian villages. (Makine, 2011: 23)

Similarly, when Olga, the “noble” woman who had been to Paris, tells them about some sensual episodes that took place in the Occident, the three teenagers in *Au Temps du fleuve Amour* conceptualize a complex cultural background and imagine a picture which bears the marks of their own neighborhood. The death of Serge Goletz, the Russian doctor of Olga Arbélina’s son, is perceived differently by the two communities of Villiers-la-Forêt; thus, the White Russians think he was the victim of (stupid) drowning, whereas the French believe Goletz is the victim of a love intrigue. In the novel *La Terre et le ciel de Jacques Dorme*, the young narrator’s companions in an orphanage wait for their fathers to come back covered in glory when in reality they had been killed for completely meaningless reasons.

Conclusion

In this context, one aspect that deserves attention is the author’s permanent vacillation between literature and history, as he is profoundly aware of all that the seventy years of communism have done to the Russian soul. In Alain Vuillemin’s words: “Fascism, communism, totalitarianism would indeed correspond to an explosion of political, profane, secular or material religions, which would be specific to the twentieth century and in which false beliefs, true spiritual illusions or genuine lies would mix inextricably. The power of dictators would rely upon a mysterious act of faith.” (Vuillemin, 1989, n.p., transl. mine)

The Stalinist repressions, the relationship of the Soviet authorities with the Western world, the collectivization, the rationed goods are realities that outrage Makine and that he evokes with bitterness. As a matter of fact, the detail that made us pay more attention to Makine’s social message is an interview that he gave in 2001 in which he denounced the Soviet totalitarianism and underlines the writer’s role in the awakening of consciousness:

The historical and ideological trial of those years is over, but the literature still has some things to say about the extreme nature of this regime, its desire to reduce the human being to its function [...] In my opinion, the task of a writer is this: to show that beyond the herd of victims or idiots, there were rebels and men who took pleasure in their role of executioners. Before these times are over there is a little time left to say that things were not as simple as they seem. [...] Only literature today can synthesize, avoid hasty schematism, abusive generalization. (our translation from Magazine *Lire*, 2001)

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